

Factorial Study of Material and Process Parameters on Fire and Mechanical Properties of Wool and Wheat Gluten Composites

FG. Bruna¹, NK. Kim^{1*}, O. Das², MS. Hedenqvist², D. Bhattacharyya¹

¹ Mechanical Engineering Department, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand

² Department of Fibre and Polymer Technology, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden

Background – Protein based Materials' Applications

Wool fibre for polymeric composites

Wool fibre, Synthetic polymer + Flame retardant, Extrusion, Self extinguishment (V-0), Wool fibre composites char formation, FR wool

(Kim, Bhattacharyya. Mater Des, 106 2016 / Jung, Bhattacharyya. ACS Sustain Chem Eng, 6(10) 2018)

Wheat gluten biopolymer

Gluten powder + Cross linker, Compression moulding, Biopolymer Sample, Gluten biopolymer char formation

Heat release rate (kW/m²) vs Time (s) graph showing WG (red) and WGJ (blue) curves.

(Das et al. J Clean Prod, 222(10) 2019)

Wool/Gluten Composites Manufacturing

- Short coarse wool fibre: 2-3 mm in length and Avg. 45 μm in diameter
- Glycerol as a plasticiser
- Compression moulding
 - Pre-heating at 70 °C and the maximum press temperature of 160 °C

Mixing (Room temperature), Granules, Hot Press, Pressed samples, Mechanical testing samples, Fire testing samples

Factorial Design of Experiment

Taguchi L8 Orthogonal Array

Sample	A. Moulding Temperature (°C)	B. Glycerol (wt.%)	Interaction factor A x B	D. Wool fibre (wt.%)	Interaction factor A x D	Interaction factor B x D
L1	140	20	1	20	1	1
L2	140	20	1	30	2	2
L3	140	30	2	20	1	2
L4	140	30	2	30	2	1
L5	160	20	2	20	2	1
L6	160	20	2	30	1	2
L7	160	30	1	20	2	2
L8	160	30	1	30	1	1

Signal to noise ratio

$$S/N = -10 \log \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 \right]$$

(smaller the better for fire testing results)

$$S/N = -10 \log \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{y_i^2} \right]$$

(larger the better for mechanical testing results)

Fire Resistant and Mechanical Properties of Wool/Gluten Composites

Fire resistant

Vertical burn test: Self Extinguishment

Heat release rate (kW/m²) vs Time (s) graph comparing Neat Gluten (black) and Wool/Gluten composite (blue).

Signal to noise ratio plot for Peak heat release rate showing various interaction points (A1, B1, AB2, D2, BD2, AD1, AD2, Avg., A2, B2, AB1, D1, BD1).

Mechanical

Sample	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Tensile stress (MPa)	Tensile Strain (%)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Stress (MPa)
Neat Gluten	3.97	16.0	0.21	3.50	28.7
Wool/Gluten composite	2.95	21.1	1.19	2.22	39.8

